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FEATURES OF DETERMINING PRESSURE LOSSES IN MAIN PRESSURE WATER PIPES

U.R.Kdirbayev, Sh.T.Rustamov

Irrigatsiya va suv muammolari ITI tayanch doktoranti, Toshkent

In the article the questions of determination of losses of pressure are considered in main ϵ o δ o δ o δ ax and ring network taking into account the recommendable values of coefficients of local resistances.

Key words: *main water pipelines, ring network, coefficient of local resistance, tee, cross, shut-off valves, socket connections.*

When designing pressure water pipelines, one of the tasks is to determine pipe diameters and pressure losses, which are necessary for selecting pumps.

Pressure losses in pipelines are divided into linear and local, the former depend on the roughness of the inner surface of the pipeline - frictional resistance along the length - and are characterized by the coefficient λ , the latter - on local resistances found on water pipelines, such as, for example, turns of pipe fittings (tees, crosses) and shut-off valves (valves, butterfly valves).

Linear pressure losses along the length are determined using the well-known Darcy-Weisbach formula. For hydraulic calculations of water pipes, the expression is usually used:

$$i = \lambda \frac{1}{d} \times \frac{V^2}{2g}$$

where: i - specific pressure loss due to friction (hydraulic slope)

Using this formula, F.A. Shevelev compiled tables for the hydraulic calculation of pipes for various materials [1].

Pressure losses due to local resistance are determined using the Weisbach formula. [2]:

$$h_M = \zeta \frac{V^2}{2g}$$

where: ζ - local resistance coefficient.

The values of local resistance coefficients are given in reference books on water supply and in textbooks on pumping stations. Due to the insignificant value of local pressure losses compared to linear ones, they are usually not determined, but are taken as a percentage of linear losses. Known recommendations on the value of local resistances in percentage according to data from different authors differ significantly from each other.

So P.A. Spysnov recommends not taking local resistance into account at all for

external networks [3]. According to the designer's handbook 1977[1] the coefficient of local resistance should be taken within 1-3% of linear ones.

V.S. Dikarevsky coefficient of local resistance for water pipelines recommends taking it equal to 1.058 [4], [5] or within the range of 1.05-1.1 [6], V.I. Turk - also within the range of 1.05-1.1 [7], P.P. Yakubchik - within 1.03-1.1 [8], M.V. Pozdneev and V.P. Sirotkin - equal to 1.1 [9], [10] and [11]. The highest value of the local resistance coefficient is recommended by Construction regulations 2.04.02-84-1.1-1.2 [12].

All given coefficient values in different sources refer, as noted, to fittings and shut-off valves, but do not affect the influence of butt joint designs, which depend on the pipe material.

The issue of the influence of socket connections on changes in the coefficient of local resistance, as a result of which pressure losses in a water pipeline made of reinforced concrete pipes increase, was considered in the work carried out at the Department of Water Supply and Sanitation of PGUPS in 1997. In the abstract for the candidate's dissertation [13] it was noted that Until now, there is no theory for determining pressure losses in butt joints similar to reinforced concrete pipes.

Experimental studies have shown that the pressure loss in a single joint of reinforced concrete pipes does not exceed 2.5 mm, and the total pressure loss in the joints is ~8% of the total pressure loss along the length. Calculation of pressure losses in a water pipeline per 1 km of length of reinforced concrete pipes with a diameter of 500 mm at a speed of ~1.0 m/s showed that they can reach 17% of the value of pressure losses along the length, which is usually not taken into account in the hydraulic calculation of pipelines.

It follows that when determining the coefficient of local resistance of water pipelines, the following must be taken into account:

the role of the pipeline in the water supply system is either a main water pipeline or a ring network;

design of butt joints, depending on the pipe material;

type of shut-off valves - gate valves or butterfly valves.

Trunk networks are characterized by a small number of turns of pipes and shut-off valves. According to Construction regulations [12], such water pipelines should be divided into repair sections no more than 5 km long when laid in two or more lines, no more than 3 km when laid in one line. (clause 8.10). The number of switchings between water pipelines is determined by calculation (clause 8.2). Ring networks are also characterized by a small number of pipe turns, but the number of shaped parts - tees and crosses and also shut-off valves - gate valves or butterfly valves - is much larger.

Socket joints, similar to reinforced concrete pipes, are available in cast iron

pipes, coupling joints are found in asbestos-cement pipes, however, the length and depth of the gap in the butt joints of these pipes is less than in reinforced concrete pipes, and therefore, it can be expected that the pressure loss due to local resistance will be less.

Joints of steel and plastic pipes made by butt welding have minimal local pressure losses, which can be neglected. The analysis of pressure losses in main water pipelines and ring networks, taking into account the recommended values of local resistance coefficients proposed by different authors, given in reference books and regulatory documents, allows us to propose the following coefficient values:

For main water pipelines:

- From reinforced concrete pipes 1.15-1.20;
- From cast iron and asbestos-cement pipes 1.05-1.10;
- From steel and plastic pipes 1.03-1.05.

For ring networks:

- From cast iron and asbestos-cement pipes 1.10-1.15;
- From steel and plastic pipes 1.05-1.10.

Lower values of the coefficients should be taken when installing valves on the water pipeline route, larger values when installing butterfly valves.

LITERATURE

1. Шевелев Ф.А., Шевелев А.Ф.. таблица для гидравлических расчетов водопроводных труб. М.: ООО “Баскет” 2008г. 351 стр.
2. Справочник проектировщика Водоснабжение населенных мест и промышленных предприятий. М.: Стройиздат 1977г. 288 стр.
3. Спышнов П.А. Проектирование водопроводов в жилых и гражданских зданиях, СИ, М. 1951г. 245 стр.
4. Дикаревский В.С., Краснянский И.И. Напорные водоводы железнодорожного водоснабжения, транспорт М. 1978г. 280 стр.
5. Дикаревский В.С. Водоводы. РАСН, М. 1997 г. 198 стр.
6. Дикаревский В.С., Якубчик П.П., Иванов В.Г., Петров Е.Г. Водоснабжение и водоотведение на железнодорожном транспорте, “Вариант”, М., 1999, 438 стр.
7. Турк В.И., Михеев А.В., Карелин В.Я. Насосы и насосные станции, СИ, М., 1976., 304 стр.
8. Якубчик П.П. Насосы и насосные станции. Учебное пособие. ПГУПС. С-Пб, 1997г. 106 стр.
9. Позднеев М.В. Уточненный метод подбора насосов. Сборник трудов ЛИИЖТа “Водоснабжение, канализация, гидравлика” вып. 1962г., 185 стр.
10. Позднеев М.В. Расчет и проектирование насосных станций. Учебное пособие. ЛИИЖТ. Л., 1962 г., 82 стр.
11. Сироткин В.П. Схемы и расчеты водоводов и водопроводных сетей. ВШ., М., 1968г., 272 стр.
12. СНиП 2.04.02-84 Водоснабжение. Наружные сети и сооружения. М.: Госстрой России, 2001 г., 128 стр.
13. Байманов К.И., Кдирбаев У.Р. Особенности проектирования и гидравлического расчёта канализационной сети. М.; Вестник. Турин Полийтехника; 2018-316-322 с